

An Analysis of Implementation of Development Program Agropolitan Area at Pidie District

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Abstract:- Rapid economic growth has created a gap between development in cities and villages. Agropolitan is an alternative solution to the problem of the development gap between cities and villages. Pidie Regency has an agricultural area that has the potential to be developed into an agropolitan area. The development of agropolitan is hampered by several obstacles so that it is not optimal. Based on these problems, this study aims to analyze the implementation of the agropolitan area development program. This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach to describe the implementation of the program. The results of the study indicated that regional development has not been fully implemented properly due to the lack of program socialization.

Keywords:- *Development, Agropolitan Area, Implementation programs.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector in rural areas, if taken seriously, can actually be a strategy for recovery as well as the backbone for the development of the real sector from the economic crisis that has been experienced by Indonesia since mid-1997. . The agricultural sector has several characteristics such as: the involvement of many people with low ownership of resources, skills and knowledge, as well as social networks that are less supportive, especially to enter the modern economic era at this time.

Rapid economic growth has made the agricultural sector sidelined, even though this sector is a key sector to ensure the quality of Indonesia's human resources while maintaining the availability of food supplies and ensuring food insecurity does not occur. So far, the measure of development success has only been seen from the creation of a high rate of economic growth where the tool used is to encourage industrialization in urban areas. This condition when viewed from the perspective of equitable development has created a gap between rural and urban areas because the strategic sector is only owned by some people who are generally located in urban areas.

Development based on local resources, using a regional approach and involving the participation of the community is the development of agropolitan areas proposed by Friedman and Douglass (1975) who offer the Agropolitan concept as a critique of the trickle down effect theory, which emphasizes development in urban centers so that the results can be achieved. dripping into the countryside.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pidie Regency has a potential area for the development of a development area based on the agropolitan concept. The terrain's topography and climate make it possible to develop various agricultural commodities, food crops, horticulture, livestock, fisheries, and plantations based on agribusiness. In this case, agropolitan development can be used as a way to accelerate rural agricultural development.

Pidie Regency has potential in the agricultural sector with an agro-climate that supports the potential in the agricultural sector with an agro-climate that supports the development of the agribusiness sector with the activities of most of its people having the main livelihood dominated by the agricultural sector. This is included in the requirements for determining the agropolitan area, because Pidie District chose the agropolitan concept as the basic concept in regional development, especially in Padang Tiji District, Sakti District, Tangse District and Mane District.

The conditions faced by Pidie Regency in the development of agropolitan are currently not maximal in agricultural production, because there are still many agribusiness actors who are subsistence (only to meet their own needs), the difficulty of obtaining production inputs (seeds and fertilizers) and the low human resources of farmers in carrying out agriculture. in a modern way.

Problems that are no less important are government policies that have not supported agropolitan development in terms of compiling regulations that strengthen agropolitan areas, socialization of the implementation of regional development that is not optimal, access to infrastructure (roads and irrigation networks) that have not been maximized, limited funds from financial institutions in the region. agropolitan and entrepreneurial spirit of agribusiness actors are still low.

This study aims to describe the implementation of the agropolitan area development program in Pidie Regency and to determine the factors that can encourage the development of the agropolitan area.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses descriptive qualitative research method which describes the research object comprehensively. Data Collection Methods Data collection techniques with systematic observations of phenomena that occur at research locations, interviews were conducted with officials and technical service staff involved in the Agropolitan Area Development Program in Pidie Regency, as well as documenting conditions in the Agropolitan Area, the people interviewed were farmers affected by the development of agropolitan areas.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on a descriptive analysis of the implementation of the agropolitan program in Pidie Regency, several obstacles were found that hindered the implementation of the agropolitan program. These constraints are as follows:

A. Implementing the Dissemination of the Agropolitan Program is Not Optimal

Program socialization is the third step in the strategy of developing an agropolitan area after designing the regional master plan and determining the agropolitan proposal. From the results of the study, data was obtained that the socialization of the agropolitan program was carried out in 2018 involving 40 farmer group leaders from the four sub-districts that were the target of the program. This socialization is considered not to explain the content and purpose, it is evident that the heads of farmer groups do not know much about agropolitan programs. The key to the success of the agropolitan program is detailed and routine socialization which is expected to change the mindset of farming business actors.

B. Agropolitan Implementing Working Group Has Not Been Formed

The implementing actors of the agropolitan area development program are, of course, organizations from both local governments and organizations in the community. These organizations are incorporated in an official forum called the Pokja (working group) implementing the development of the agropolitan area of Pidie Regency. However, to date, the working group responsible for implementing the program has not been officially formed. The program is still being implemented by the respective agencies, namely Bappeda and the Department of Agriculture and Food.

The formation of a working group for the development of the Agropolitan area of Pidie Regency is one manifestation of the development of district government policies. This is considered by researchers as an effort to internally strengthen the local government of Pidie Regency because members of the Pokja Team are the Top Leaders of each SKPK related to the implementation of policies for developing the Pidie Regency Agropolitan area.

C. Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

Based on the findings in the field, that the SOP for Agropolitan in Pidie Regency does not yet exist, the absence of the SOP indicates that the implementation of the development of the Agropolitan area in Pidie Regency is not ideal and will affect the implementation process of the policy itself. With the SOP, SKPK can carry out their activities according to the specified corridor.

V. CONCLUSION

- Implementation of the Development of the Pidie Regency Agropolitan Area
 - Based on a descriptive analysis of the implementation of the development of the Agropolitan area of Pidie Regency, it can be concluded several things as follows: (1) The implementation of the Agropolitan area development program is not optimal, this is because the socialization of the agropolitan program to farmers in the agropolitan area has not been maximized; (2) The organization implementing the activities, namely the Agropolitan Working Group Team has not yet been formed so that there is no coordination between the relevant agencies; (4) There is no Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) so that there is no reference in implementing program activities, (5) Lack of program information so that most farmers in the agropolitan area do not know about the agropolitan area development program which causes farmers to be less interested in the development of the agropolitan area.
 - The results of multiple linear regression analysis show that the factors of providing production inputs, infrastructure development, increasing farmer human resources, the role of institutions and government policies have a significant effect in encouraging the implementation of the agropolitan area development program in Pidie Regency.

VI. SUGGESTION

Based on the results of the research, several suggestions are proposed so that the development of agropolitan areas in Pidie Regency can be maximized, as follows:

- The Pidie Regency Government must immediately issue a decision letter to determine the Pokja (Working Group) for the Agropolitan Area Development Program in Pidie Regency, so that the agencies related to agropolitan development can direct its implementation optimally. Relevant agencies are also advised to develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) so that they are clear in the main tasks and functions of each service.
- Criteria for providing inputs, infrastructure, institutions, and policies can be used as complements in developing agropolitan areas in addition to improving human resources and technology aimed at increasing processing and managerial capabilities of farmers and MSME group associations.

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